

VERTICAL HEAT TRANSFER OF ALUMINIUM COMPOSITE CLADDINGS

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ABSTRACT

Recent catastrophic events involving fires in multi-storey buildings such as the Grenfell Tower fire (UK, 2017) involving combustible aluminium composite panels (ACPs) have led to substantial loss of lives. Combustible panel cores and insulation materials, mostly polyethylene, drastically facilitates the propagation of fire along the height of the structure which imposes challenges in fire safety. The purpose of this research was to investigate the propagation of temperature vertically in modern façade systems with the use of ACP cladding subjected to both static and dynamic heat fluxes. Three different types of ACP with different combustibility namely FR, PE and NC, were tested in the experiments. It was found that the degradation of PE samples for increasing heating regime started at a heat flux lower than that for static conditions. Moreover, the total energy reaching the surface of the sample by that time for increasing regime was lower (6542 kJ/m²) than for static (7600 kJ/m²).

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite claddings have been used in the construction industry globally for building facades and internal structures. Aluminium composite panel (ACP) is a type of sandwich panel composed of two thin skin layers of aluminium bonded to a polymer core. However, recent catastrophic events involving fires in multi-storey buildings which have occurred worldwide in the UAE, Australia, China, and the UK were caused by the use of combustible composite panels in exterior walls [1, 2], which have led to substantial loss of lives and resources. One of the main contributors to these fire incidents is due to the rapid movement of fire along the building or vertical propagation of flame caused by combustible facades [3].

It is known that ignition and combustion are essentially dependent on the type of the heat flux, whether it is static or variable (when the ignition of materials is initiated by the time-dependent heat flux). Most of previous research has used static heat flux, while in real conditions the dynamic heating regimes are observed during fires. Overall, most of investigators try to see “a big picture” and the processes and phenomena occurring at a small scale has not been given enough attention. A good exception is a study of [1], where they used a range of micro- and bench-scale methods to understand the fire behaviour of different types of façade product in order to explain the speed, ferocity and lethality of the fire. In their study samples 70 × 70 mm² were tested horizontally at an applied constant heat flux of 50 kW m⁻², following ISO 5660 [4]. They tested different types of ACP, such as polyethylene (PE), PE filled with metal hydroxide fire retardant (FR), and predominantly non-combustible (NC), such as inorganic composite or metallic filling, and showed that polyethylene-aluminium composites were the most hazardous. It was shown, that only a few burning drips of polyethylene from the panelling are

enough to ignite the foam insulation. The aim of this paper was to assess the propagation of temperature vertically in modern façade systems using ACPs exposed to static and dynamic heat fluxes.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Description and preparation of the samples

Three types of ACP panels were investigated with different core types: NC panels consist of non-combustible inorganic matrix core, FR-PE panels consist of low-density polyethylene (PE) core with non-combustible minerals, and pure PE panels with standard polyethylene core. The panels were cut into 60 cm x 5 cm samples. As the temperature distribution throughout the panel is desired, Type K glass braided insulated thermocouple wires (TC) were fixed, by drilling holes, along the height and width of the samples. The panels were divided into 6 sections (A-F) 10 cm each, 4 TCs were soldered to 12 mm x 0.2 mm copper discs to measure temperatures in the unexposed surface of the sample (A,C,E,F), 6 TCs inserted into the core (A-F short TCs), and 6 TCs were fixed inside up to the face of the exposed aluminium sheet to measure the temperature where direct heating was. Thermo-gravimetric analysis was also utilised to investigate the pyrolysis reaction of the cladding core.

2.2 Experimental Procedure

For each condition, three experiments were conducted. A custom-made radiative heat flux apparatus was used to simulate the static and variable conditions. The radiative heat flux was produced through infrared short-wave quartz lamps. Only the lowest module of the apparatus was turned on, where section F experienced direct heating from the lamp. The apparatus is installed on a 1.5m linear stage which allows it to move forward or backward to replicate dynamic heat flux. Three heating regimes were simulated; static, increasing and decreasing regimes. A static heat flux of 50 kW/m² for 30 minutes was simulated for static conditions, a time-temperature rise curve was utilised for increasing conditions from Eq (1). Lastly, for decreasing regime, data from [5] were extrapolated to higher heat fluxes and used to simulate the influence of the sprinkler system.

$$T=345\log_{10}(8t+1)+20 \quad (1)$$

3 RESULTS AND FINDINGS

3.1 Pyrolysis reaction

The pyrolysis reaction of the PE, FR and NC core was evaluated through thermogravimetric analysis in combination with the modified Coats-Redfern and Kissinger methods [6]. Based on the TGA data the degree of decomposition of each material was calculated according to Eq. (2-5). For further details of the developed methods, please refer to [7].

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT}=(1-\alpha)^n \cdot \frac{A}{\beta} \cdot e^{-\frac{E_A}{RT}}$$

$$\alpha \approx \frac{ART^2}{\beta E_A} \left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E_A}\right) \cdot e^{-\frac{E_A}{RT}} \quad (3)$$

$$-\ln\left(\frac{\alpha}{T^2}\right) = \frac{E_A}{RT} - \ln \frac{AR}{\beta E_A} \left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E_A}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{E_A\beta}{RT_m^2} = An(1-\alpha_m)^{n-1} e^{-\frac{E_A}{RT_m}} \quad (5)$$

where α is the degree of decomposition of pyrolysis reaction at temperature T , β is the heating rate, A is the pre-exponential factor, E_A is the activation energy, n is the reaction order, R is the universal gas constant and T_m is the critical temperature at which the maximum rate of reaction occurs.

A thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed for samples of 10 – 20 mg which were subjected to a gradual rise in temperature inside a furnace in an inert nitrogen using a Stanton Redcroft STA 780 (Figure 1) at a heating rate of $10^0\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Figure 1: TGA results of PE, FR and NC samples

Figure 2 illustrates the linear correlation between $(1/T)$ and $(-\ln(\alpha/T^2))$.

Figure 2. Evaluation of E_A for polyethylene (blue line) and the mineral filler in NC core (red lines). Continuous curves are data calculated using the modified Coat-Redfern and Kissinger method while the corresponding dotted line is used to calculate the slope.

As seen in Figure 12, the slopes of these curves give the value of E_A/R [7]. The pre-exponential factor, activation energy and reaction order were then calculated according to the method prescribed earlier in this section and shown in Table 1.

	PE	NC
Pre-exponential factor A, (1/s)	$7.73 * 10^{27}$	1,710,859
Activation energy E_A , (J/mol)	401,354	77,002
Reaction order, n	2.21	1.79
Critical temperature T_m , (°C)	474	309

Table 1: Calculated kinetic parameters of PE and NC materials.

3.2 Vertical heat transfer

The PE samples were found to have degraded at a lower heat flux with increasing regime than for static conditions. The total energy experienced by the surface of the panel for increasing regime (6542 kJ/m²) was lower than for static conditions (7600 kJ/m²). This shows the severity of effects in static conditions can be experienced at lower energies with increasing regimes. As for the decreasing regime, the core degraded but not as much as it stayed intact and solid.

Based from the temperature developments (Figure 3), the highest temperature always occurred in section F where the direct source of heating was. However, it was observed that the TCs located in the middle (core) had higher temperatures than temperatures on the exposed side of the aluminium in sections A-E, which may be due to the strong updraft airflow and to the higher amount of energy being absorbed than taken by convection. It was also observed that pyrolysis started after 100°C which was followed by the degradation of core which started at 200 °C.

The NC panels, when exposed to all heating regimes, were resistant to fire in contrast to FR and PE panels. No melting and flaming of core were observed during the tests except for the delamination of aluminium in section F. On the other hand, the core of FR samples expanded then melted. The expansion of core was more than double (5-10mm) of the initial thickness for all heating regimes. The exposed aluminium sheet melted during the increasing regime which showed the effect of a more severe heating condition. As for the pure PE samples, the combustible core melted continuously that caused ignition and flaming which occurred about only 12 minutes into the test. The polymer matrix proved to have a severe degradation under high temperatures [8]. The aluminium was also observed to delaminate completely before it melted due to flame (Figure 4). While drippings from the PE core is enough to cause ignition [2], it was found that the temperature measurements at the unexposed surface were high enough (up to 565°C) which indicates a possible ignition source for materials in contact with the panel, such as the insulation. Figure 4a shows a sequence of photos during the test for PE samples exposed to increasing heat flux, the highest temperature reached about 700°C in increasing heating regime and about 600°C in static regime.

The temperature profiles for static and dynamic for FR and NC showed similar maximum temperatures. However, FR PE and PE panels were more reactive than NC samples, which have caused higher temperatures.

Figure 3: Temperature development of PE-ACP exposed to increasing heat flux

Figure 4: Photos of panels during and after exposed to increasing heat flux

4. CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of the experimental results showed that A1 panel was resistant to fire, without any expansion and melting of the core while PE panels were more thermally degradable. The core was melting and expanding under the heating, with exposed aluminium sheet burned out at increasing heating regime. None of the samples had flaming ignition or combustion except for the pure PE samples. Visual observations also showed that PE samples produced much more smoke than A1 panels. Among the three panels investigated, pure PE samples recorded the highest temperatures for the unexposed surface for static and increasing regime. Temperature measurements indicated that unexposed surface temperature for all panels were high enough (up to 565 °C) to act as a secondary heat/ignition source for insulation or other materials in contact with the panels.

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